

LOW-POWER RETENTIVE TRUE SINGLE PHASE CLOCKED FLIP FLOP WITH REDUNDANT PRECHARGE FREE OPERATION

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Abstract: As digital systems improve, power consumption has become a critical limitation, especially with the rapid growth of battery-powered IoT devices. Flip-flops (FFs), essential components of digital circuits, contribute significantly to power usage. Therefore, reducing FF power consumption can substantially lower the overall power of digital systems. Voltage scaling is a promising technique for reducing power consumption, but it requires FFs capable of operating efficiently at both super-threshold and near-/sub-threshold voltages. The transmission-gate flip-flop (TGFF), widely used for its contention-free operation, is suitable for near-threshold applications. However, its large clock network and toggling internal nodes (CKN and CKI) lead to high power consumption, even with low data activity. Optimizing complementary clock signals can help reduce this power consumption. While several low-power, single-phase-clocked FFs have been proposed, challenges such as failure at low voltages or high precharge power remain. This project proposes a novel energy-efficient, retentive true single-phase-clocked (TSPC) FF. The key innovation is an input-aware precharge scheme that activates precharging only when necessary, minimizing power usage. Additionally, floating node analysis and transistor-level optimizations will enhance energy efficiency without significantly increasing area. The proposed TSPC FF is expected to reduce power consumption by over 80% and delay by up to 30%, with minimal area overhead compared to TGFFs.

Key words - Flip-flop (FF), low voltage operation, low-power, redundant-precharge-free, true-single-phase-clocked (TSPC)

I. Introduction

With advances in digital system design, performance has significantly improved, but power consumption has become a major limitation. The rapid growth of the Internet of Things (IoT) [1] has led to large-scale deployment of IoT devices, many of which are battery-powered or self-powered. As a result, low-power design has become a critical focus. Flip-flops (FFs), as fundamental components of digital circuits [2], contribute significantly to overall power consumption. Therefore, reducing the power consumption of FFs can have a substantial impact on the energy efficiency of digital systems [3]. One effective approach to reducing power consumption is voltage scaling, which has proven to be a promising technique. To fully benefit

from voltage scaling, FFs must be designed to operate efficiently at both super-threshold and near-/sub-threshold supply voltages. The transmission-gate flip-flop (TGFF) [4] is the most commonly used FF in modern digital systems. The schematic of the TGFF is shown below.

Figure 1 TCF

The transmission-gate flip-flop (TGFF) is a contention-free flip-flop [5], making it well-suited for near-threshold voltage operation. However, its main drawback lies in the large clock network. The internal nodes, CKN [6] and CKI [7], toggle regardless of input data, which drives a larger number of transistors and results in higher power consumption—even when data activity is low. To reduce FF power consumption, optimizing the use of complementary clock signals is crucial. Although several low-power, single-phase-clocked FFs have been proposed, many still face challenges, such as failure at low supply voltages or excessive precharge power. To address these issues, this article proposes a low-power true-single-phase-clocked (TSPC) FF [8]. The proposed FF is contention-free and capable of operating over a wide supply voltage range. Additionally, redundant precharge operations are eliminated, leading to further power consumption reduction compared to previous low-power FF designs. The rest of the article is organized as follows: Section II reviews several popular low-power FFs, Section III presents a detailed description of the proposed FF, Section IV displays simulation results and experimental results.

II. Reviews several popular low power Flip Flops

The Internet of Things:

The Internet of Things (IoT) [9] has been inscription in this review paper. Internet of Things is a keyword to cover various challenges related to internet and the web to the real physical world. We know that, today internet has already taken an important part of everyday life and it has also dramatically changed the lives of human being. The most important factor of this invention is, integration or combination of several technologies [10] with the communication system solutions [11]. The most applicable factors of IoT is the identification and tracking

various factors for smart objects. The universal sensing networks is enabled by Wireless Sensing Networks (WSN) [12] and these technologies cuts across many areas of modernday living. The escalation of these devices in a communicating and actuating network will create the Internet of Things (IoT). Here the sensors and actuators combine easily with the environment around us and the information is shared across various platforms in order to develop a common operating picture (COP) [13].

Internet of Things predicts the future that, the advance digital world and the physical world will get linked by means of proper information and wireless communication system technologies. In this survey paper we have mentioned the visions, concepts, technologies, various challenges, some innovation directions, and various applications of Internet of Things (IoT).

Wearable healthcare devices are essential for daily health monitoring and safe exercise, with health prediction systems helping reduce the risk of sudden death through early warnings. Cardiovascular diseases and sudden cardiac arrest account for the largest share of global deaths (31% in 2012). Continuous heart monitoring using electrocardiography (ECG) in wearable devices enables preventive measures for at-risk individuals [14].

This brief presents an ultralow power ECG feature extraction engine, which extracts key features like the QRS complex, P-wave, and T-wave to diagnose cardiovascular conditions. The extraction uses a combination of curve length transform (CLT) [15] and discrete wavelet transform. A novel pipelined CLT architecture was implemented in a system fabricated with GF-65-nm technology, consuming just 642 nW at 7.5 kHz and 0.6 V. The low power consumption makes this system ideal for self-powered wearable devices.

Ultra-low power QRS detection and ECG compression architecture for IOT healthcare devices:

This paper presents an ultra-low power ECG [16] processing architecture for IoT medical wearables, focusing on real-time QRS detection and ECG compression. A novel absolute-value curve length transform (A-CLT) enhances QRS detection while minimizing hardware requirements, using only adders, shifters, and comparators, eliminating multipliers. The QRS detection achieved 99.37% sensitivity and 99.38% predictivity when validated with the Physionet ECG database. Additionally, a lossless compression technique using the ECG signal's first derivative and entropy encoding achieved an average compression ratio of 2.05 on the MIT-BIH database. The architecture addresses ECG artifacts (e.g., noise, baseline drift) with minimal hardware. Implemented in 65-nm low-power process, the design consumes just 6.5 nW at 1 V and 250 Hz, benefiting from duty-cycling for further energy efficiency.

An energy-precision scalable parallel Ultra Low power soc for IOT edge processing:

Most ultra-low-power smart-sensing edge devices [17], powered by small batteries, handle low-bandwidth sensors like temperature or pressure, focusing on minimal power

consumption at the cost of performance. To reduce power, many designs use sub-threshold processors operating at low frequencies (kHz to MHz). This paper presents *Mr. Wolf*, a parallel ultra-low-power (PULP) SoC with a hierarchical architecture. It features a 12 kgates RISC-V microcontroller (MCU) core and an autonomous IO subsystem for efficient data transfer from peripherals. The MCU offloads compute-intensive tasks to an eight-core floating-point engine. Built on a 40-nm LP CMOS process, it includes 512 kB of fully retentive memory consuming 108 μ W. The IO subsystem transfers data at 1.6 Gbit/s with 2.5 mW power consumption. The eight-core compute cluster achieves peak performance of 850 MMAC/s and 500 MFMAC/s, with energy efficiency of 15 MMAC/s/mW and 9 MFMAC/s/mW. The SoC, supported by efficient on-chip power management, enables heterogeneous computing for always-on IoT nodes, delivering significant performance improvements within a 153 mW power envelope. Demonstrations on real-life near-sensor processing show that *Mr. Wolf* achieves kMOp/s/mW, enabling always-on data analytics for high-bandwidth sensors at the IoT edge.

A Near-Threshold, Sub-0.4-mW, 16Core Programmable Spatial Array Accelerator for the Ultralow-Power Mobile and Embedded Internet of Things:

Ultralow voltage programmable spatial array accelerators, or coarse-grain reconfigurable arrays (CGRAs) [18], have gained significant interest for their power, performance, and area (PPA) [19] advantages over traditional computing platforms like microprocessors and FPGAs. These accelerators offer flexibility to adapt to various workloads with a one-time non-recurring engineering (NRE) investment [20].

The Next Generation 64b SPARC Core in a T4 SoC Processor:

Oracle's T-series processors, starting with the T1, have continually improved aggregate throughput performance for commercial workloads. While throughput has doubled per generation (T1–T3), single-thread integer performance remained constant. The T4 processor addresses this gap with an out-of-order, dual-issue S3 core, delivering up to 5x integer and 7x floating-point single-thread improvements while maintaining throughput and power efficiency. It features eight cores, a 4 MB L3 cache, 2.4 Tb/s I/O bandwidth, and advanced power management in a 40nm, 406 mm² die with 855 million transistors. Enhanced physical design supports high performance with reduced power challenges [21].

A 0.4V 0.5fJ/cycle TSPC Flip-Flop in 65nm LP CMOS with Retention Mode Controlled by Clock- Gating Cells:

Flip-flops (FFs) are crucial in digital circuits, contributing significantly to area and power. In a 65nm LP CMOS ARM Cortex-M0 CPU, FFs consume 40% of area and 30% of power. This paper introduces a 19T TSPC FF with retention mode for ultra-low voltage (ULV) operation. A retention feedback loop ensures contention-free data retention during clock gating, reducing energy overhead. The proposed FF, implemented in 65nm LP CMOS, achieves 0.5fJ/cycle at 0.4V, a 62% energy reduction compared to a conventional 24T FF. Validation on a Cortex-M0 test chip confirms robust ULV performance.

Quasi-Static Voltage Scaling for Energy Minimization with Time Constraints:

Dynamic Voltage Scaling (DVS) [22] and Adaptive Body Biasing (ABB) [23] enable energy-performance trade-offs by adjusting voltage and frequency. DVS reduces dynamic power, while ABB lowers leakage power. Voltage scaling methods are offline (pre-calculated settings) or online (runtime adjustments). Offline approaches avoid runtime overhead but rely on worst-case execution times (WCET) [24], leading to conservative energy savings. Online methods adapt to real-time execution but incur computational costs. To balance these, a quasi-static voltage scaling (QSVS) scheme is proposed, combining low online complexity with increased slack exploitation, enhancing energy savings without runtime recalculation overhead. 32 Bit $\times$ 32 Bit multi precision Razor-Based Dynamic Voltage Scaling Multiplier with Operands Scheduler:

The growing demand for portable, high-performance devices requires low-power components, especially multipliers in DSPs. Traditional fixed-width multipliers waste energy due to unnecessary switching activity. This paper introduces a multi-precision (MP) [25] reconfigurable multiplier that adapts precision, frequency, and voltage to workload demands. It combines variable precision, parallel processing, razor-based dynamic voltage scaling (DVS), and an operand scheduler for optimal performance and power efficiency. Fabricated in 0.35- μ m technology, the MP multiplier reduces area by 28.2%, power by 15.8%, and achieves up to 86.3% total power savings with minimal 11.1% area overhead, demonstrating enhanced energy efficiency.

A Self-Tuning IoT Processor Using Leakage- Ratio Measurement for Energy-Optimal Operation:

Wireless IoT sensors are power-constrained due to miniaturization and require energy-efficient operation for long battery life. This paper combines dynamic voltage scaling (DVS) and adaptive body biasing (ABB) to achieve energy-optimal operation by dynamically adjusting supply voltage and body bias based on the leakage-to-dynamic power ratio. Implemented on a Cortex-M0 processor with a custom dc-dc converter and SRAM in a 55-nm DDC CMOS, the design achieves 6.4 pJ/cycle at 0.55V and 500 kHz, with energy consumption within 4.6% of optimal across process corners and temperatures from -20°C to 125°C.

Low-power and high-speed flip-flop suitable for mobile application SoCs:

Area, power, and speed are critical in SoC design, with flip-flops (F/Fs) influencing 30% power dissipation, 10% critical path delay, and 25% area. Existing F/Fs like SAFF, HLFF, and SDFP balance speed and power but face limitations for high-performance mobile SoCs [26]. This paper introduces the Cross Charge-Control Flip-Flop (XCFF), achieving 48% lower power-delay product than CMOS F/Fs and enabling 10% power savings in a 125-MHz microprocessor core without speed or area penalties. Additionally, the Embedded Logic Flip-Flop (ELFF) merges logic functions into F/Fs, reducing area, delay, and power by eliminating a gate delay. Scaling in VLSI technology has increased on-chip transistors and power demands, necessitating

advanced methodologies and libraries for high-performance chip design. Static F/Fs preserve values using feedback, while dynamic F/Fs require charge refreshment.

This paper presents a low-power, area-efficient shift register using static differential sense amp shared pulse latches (SSASPL) instead of flip-flops, reducing power and area. Timing issues are addressed using multiple non-overlapping delayed pulsed clock signals, grouping latches into sub-registers, and incorporating temporary storage latches. A 32-bit SSASPL-based shift register [27], designed in a 120nm CMOS process ($V_{DD} = 1.2V$), achieves better efficiency than conventional designs. Shift registers, crucial for data storage/transfer, are vital in applications like digital filters, communication receivers, and image processing, where increasing image sizes demand longer registers. Keywords: SSASPL, Flip-flop, Pulsed latch, Shift register.

III. Proposed Flip Flop

In this section, several state-of-the-art low-power FFs are reviewed and the limitations are analyzed. All the listed FFs are single-phase-clocked FFs, which optimize the number of transistors related to the clock signal compared to TGFF.

Figure 2 XCF

Figure 3 ACFF

Figure 4 TCFF

Figure 5 SPC 18T

Figure 6 S2CFF

Figure 7 RTFF

This text evaluates flip-flop (FF) designs for power efficiency and robustness at low supply voltages:

1. **XCFF**: Reduces power via charge gate capacitance control but suffers from strong current contention and wasteful precharge/discharge operations.
2. **ACFF**: Uses single-channel transmission gates to lower clock-related transistor count but is vulnerable to process variations and current contention, limiting low-voltage performance.
3. **TCFF**: Reduces clock load and area via topological compression but suffers from voltage drops and low robustness under low voltage.
4. **SPC-18T FF**: Simplifies logic to save power but has redundant precharge/discharge and short-circuit paths that reduce robustness and increase hold time at low voltage.
5. **S2CFF**: Solves internal-node retention issues for low-voltage operation but wastes energy in redundant precharge/discharge operations.
6. **RTFF**: Offers retention but has temporary short-circuit paths, voltage drops in internal nodes, and inefficient precharge/discharge processes that degrade low-voltage robustness and waste power.

Each design shows trade-offs in power, robustness, and efficiency, highlighting the challenges of optimizing FFs for low-voltage SoC applications.

Figure 8 Transient waveform of S²CFF

IV. Results and Conclusion

In this article, an energy-efficient retentive TSPC FF is proposed. By removing redundant precharge and discharge operations with the input-aware precharge scheme, the power of the proposed FF is greatly reduced. Furthermore, floating node analysis is applied to the proposed structure to avoid the generation of short-circuit paths. Then, transistor level optimizations are applied to the circuit to further reduce the area and power consumption. Post layout simulation results show that the proposed FF saves more than 80% power consumption compared with TGFF under 10% data activity. Measurement results of ten test chips also demonstrate that the proposed FF has a significant energy efficiency improvement compared with TGFF. The CK-to-Q delay of the proposed FF is 26.18% lower than that of TGFF. The area of the proposed FF is just 4.8% larger than that of TGFF, indicating little area overhead to achieve such benefits.

Flip Flop	Delay(n-Sec)	Area(nm*nm)	Power(μ W)	PDP(10^{-15} W-Sec)
TGFF	0.25	0.127	94.16	0.01195
XCFF	0.244	0.151	9.271	0.001399
ACFF	0.286	0.129	22.92	0.002956
TCFF	0.404	0.463	76.71	0.03551
SPC-18 T	0.46	0.197	4.01	0.00789
SSCFF	0.446	0.26	8.57	0.00222
Proposed	0.494	0.309	16	0.00496

REFERENCES:

- [1] L. Atzori, A. Iera, and G. Morabito, "The Internet of Things: A survey," *Comput. Netw.*, vol. 54, no. 15, pp. 2787–2805, Oct. 2010.
- [2] T. Tekeste, H. Saleh, B. Mohammad, A. Khandoker, and M. Ismail, "A nano-watt ECG feature extraction engine in 65-nm technology," *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. II, Exp. Briefs*, vol. 65, no. 8, pp. 1099–1103, Aug. 2018.
- [3] T. Tekeste, H. Saleh, B. Mohammad, and M. Ismail, "Ultra-low power QRS detection and ECG compression architecture for IoT healthcare devices," *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. I, Reg. Papers*, vol. 66, no. 2, pp. 669–679, Feb. 2019.
- [4] A. Pullini, D. Rossi, I. Loi, G. Tagliavini, and L. Benini, "Mr. Wolf: An energy-precision scalable parallel ultra low power SoC for IoT edge processing," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 54, no. 7, pp. 1970–1981, Jul. 2019.
- [5] J. P. Cerqueira, T. J. Repetti, Y. Pu, S. Priyadarshi, M. A. Kim, and M. Seok, "Catena: A nearthreshold, sub-0.4-mW, 16-core programmable spatial array accelerator for the ultralowpower mobile and embedded Internet of Things," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 55, no. 8, pp. 2270–2284, Aug. 2020.

- [6] J. L. Shin et al., “The next generation 64b SPARC core in a T4 SoC processor,” *IEEE J. SolidState Circuits*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 82–90, Jan. 2013.
- [7] L. Moreau, R. Dekimpe, and D. Bol, “A 0.4 V 0.5fJ/cycle TSPC flipflop in 65 nm LP CMOS with retention mode controlled by clockgating cells,” in *Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Circuits Syst. (ISCAS)*, May 2019, pp. 1–4.
- [8] A. Andrei, P. Eles, O. Jovanovic, M. Schmitz, J. Ogniewski, and Z. Peng, “Quasi-static voltage scaling for energy minimization with time constraints,” *IEEE Trans. Very Large Scale Integr. (VLSI) Syst.*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 10–23, Jan. 2011.
- [9] X. Zhang et al., “32bit×32bit multiprecision razor-based dynamic voltage scaling multiplier with operands scheduler,” *IEEE Trans. Very Large Scale Integr. (VLSI) Syst.*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 759–770, Apr. 2014.
- [10] W.-J. Tsou et al., “Digital low-dropout regulator with anti PVT-variation technique for dynamic voltage scaling and adaptive voltage scaling multicore processor,” in *IEEE Int. SolidState Circuits Conf. (ISSCC) Dig. Tech. Papers*, Feb. 2017, pp. 338–339.
- [11] S. Jain, L. Lin, and M. Alioto, “Dynamically adaptable pipeline for energy-efficient microarchitectures under wide voltage scaling,” *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 53, no. 2, pp. 632–641, Feb. 2018.
- [12] J. Lee et al., “A self-tuning IoT processor using leakage-ratio measurement for energyoptimal operation,” *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 55, no. 1, pp. 87–97, Jan. 2020.
- [13] A. Hirata, K. Nakanishi, M. Nozoe, and A. Miyoshi, “The cross chargecontrol flip-flop: A low-power and high-speed flip-flop suitable for mobile application SoCs,” in *Dig. Tech. Papers. Symp. VLSI Circuits*, Jun. 2005, pp. 306–307.
- [14] C. K. Teh, T. Fujita, H. Hara, and M. Hamada, “A 77% energy-saving 22-transistor singlephase-clocking D-flip-flop with adaptive-coupling configuration in 40 nm CMOS,” in *IEEE Int. Solid-State Circuits Conf. (ISSCC) Dig. Tech. Papers*, Feb. 2011, pp. 338–339.
- [15] N. Kawai et al., “A fully static topologically-compressed 21-transistor flip-flop with 75% power saving,” *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 49, no. 11, pp. 2526–2533, Nov. 2014.
- [16] Y. Cai, A. Savanth, P. Prabhat, J. Myers, A. S. Weddell, and T. J. Kazmierski, “Ultra-low power 18-transistor fully static contentionfree single-phase clocked flip-flop in 65-nm CMOS,” *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 54, no. 2, pp. 550–559, Feb. 2019.
- [17] Y. Kim et al., “A static contention-free single-phase-clocked 24T flip flop in 45 nm for low-power applications,” in *IEEE Int. Solid-State Circuits Conf. (ISSCC) Dig. Tech. Papers*, Feb. 2014, pp. 466–467.

- [18] F. Stas and D. Bol, "A 0.4-V 0.66-fJ/cycle retentive true-single-phaseclock 18T flip-flop in 28-nm fully-depleted SOI CMOS," *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. I, Reg. Papers*, vol. 65, no. 3, pp. 935–945, Mar. 2018.
- [19] F. S. Alghareb, R. A. Ashraf, and R. F. DeMara, "Designing and evaluating redundancybased soft-error masking on a continuum of energy versus robustness," *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Comput.*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 139–152, Jul. 2018.
- [20] P. E. Dodd, M. R. Shaneyfelt, J. R. Schwank, and J. A. Felix, "Current and future challenges in radiation effects on CMOS electronics," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 1747–1763, Aug. 2010.
- [21] M. Fazeli, A. Patooghy, S. G. Miremadi, and A. Ejlali, "Feedback redundancy: A power efficient SEU-tolerant latch design for deep sub-micron technologies," in *Proc. 37th Annu. IEEE/IFIP Int. Conf. Dependable Syst. Netw. (DSN)*, Jun. 2007, pp. 276–285.
- [22] Z. Huang, "A high performance SEU-tolerant latch for nanoscale CMOS technology," in *Proc. Design, Automat. Test Eur. Conf. Exhib. (DATE)*, 2014, pp. 1–5.
- [23] F. S. Alghareb, R. Zand, and R. F. Demara, "Non-volatile spintronic flipflop design for energy-efficient SEU and DNU resilience," *IEEE Trans. Magn.*, vol. 55, no. 3, pp. 1–11, Mar. 2019.
- [24] S. Kumar, S. Chellappa, and L. T. Clark, "Temporal pulse-clocked multibit flip-flop mitigating SET and SEU," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Circuits Syst. (ISCAS)*, May 2015, pp. 814–817.
- [25] J.-F. Lin, M.-H. Sheu, Y.-T. Hwang, C.-S. Wong, and M.-Y. Tsai, "Lowpower 19-transistor true single-phase clocking flip-flop design based on logic structure reduction schemes," *IEEE Trans. Very Large Scale Integr. (VLSI) Syst.*, vol. 25, no. 11, pp. 3033–3044, Nov. 2017.
- [26] S. D. Naffziger, G. Colon-Bonet, T. Fischer, R. Riedlinger, T. J. Sullivan, and T. Grutkowski, "The implementation of the Itanium 2 microprocessor," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 37, no. 11, pp. 1448–1460, Nov. 2002.
- [27] H. Jeong, J. Park, S. C. Song, and S.-O. Jung, "Self-timed pulsed latch for low-voltage operation with reduced hold time," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 54, no. 8, pp. 2304–2315, Aug. 2019